

Dispersion and characterizations of nanofluids prepared with CuO and CNT nanoparticle

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Abstract : Three types of nanofluids were prepared using copper oxide nanopowder and water, ethylene glycol (EG), and ethylene glycol : water (60 : 40) as base fluids separately. These three nanofluids were characterized by viscosity, UV-Visible spectra, dispersion stability, thermal conductivity and TEM analysis. A different type of nanofluid has also been prepared with polypropylene glycol (PPG) base fluid and carbon nanotube (CNT). The polypropylene glycol based nanofluid was characterized by thermal conductivity and TEM analysis. It was found that EG : water (60 : 40) based CuO nanofluid with sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) surfactant forms better dispersion and it was justified by the TEM analysis. The thermal conductivity enhancement of EG : water (60 : 40) based CuO nanofluid with SLS surfactant was maximum (20%) among the three nanofluids. However, polypropylene glycol based CNT nanofluid with SLS surfactant forms best dispersion as revealed by TEM analysis and had highest thermal conductivity enhancement (50%).

Keywords : Nanofluids, dispersions, thermal conductivity, TEM analysis.

Introduction

When nanoparicles are suspended in base fluids such as water, oil, ethylene glycol etc., the resulting suspensions are called “nanofluids”. The nanolayer works as a thermal bridge between the liquid base fluid and the solid nanoparticles. Nanofluids clearly exhibit improved thermo-physical properties such as thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, viscosity and convective heat transfer coefficient. The property change of nanofluids depends on the volumetric fraction of nanoparticles, shape and size of the nanomaterials¹.

Nanofluids consist of a base fluid having nano-sized solid particles (1–100 nm) suspended within them. The nanosize particle may be either a metal or metal oxide which increases thermal conductivity, when compared with base fluid or coolant. Many researches have been undertaken on the enhanced heat transfer characteristics of nanofluids, especially thermal conductivity and convective heat transfer^{2–11}.

Xie *et al.*¹² and Lee *et al.*¹³ studied the thermal conductivity of nanofluids under varying pH conditions. Xie *et al.*¹² were the first to show that the thermal conducti-

ivity of Al₂O₃ nanofluids increases gradually as the difference between the pH value of nanofluids and the isoelectric point of Al₂O₃ nanoparticle increases. Lee *et al.*¹³ found that the thermal conductivity of CuO nanofluids increased by a factor of 3 as pH decreased from the point of zero charge (PZC) of 8 to 3, indicating that thermal conductivity CuO nanofluids is strongly pH-dependent.

Nanofluids can be used as metalworking coolant fluids for grinding and polishing components. Solar energy systems can take advantage of nanofluids to enhance heat transfer from solar collectors to storage tanks. Also, nanofluids can improve the heat transfer capabilities of current industrial HVAC and refrigeration systems. Many innovative concepts are being considered; e.g. one involves the pumping of coolant from one location, where the refrigeration unit is housed to another location. Other potential nuclear applications include light water reactor coolants, standby safety system, spent-fuel storage pool, fusion diverters, etc. Nanofluids can also be designed for properties other than industrial heat transfer. For example, in the biomedical field, magnetic nanoparticles can be dispersed in blood, can be guided magnetically to a can-

cerous tumor, and then a laser or magnetic field can be used to transfer energy to the particles to destroy the tumor without significantly heating the blood or damaging nearby healthy tissue. Targeted local delivery of drugs or radiation would also be possible using magnetically-guided nanoparticles in the blood stream¹⁴.

There are many applications of nanofluids such as in heat transfer^{15,16}, electronics¹⁷, transportation¹⁸, industrial cooling and nuclear system cooling¹⁹, space and defense²⁰, mass transfer enhancement²¹, energy storage²², friction reduction²³, magnetic sealing²⁴, antibacterial activity²⁵ and in nano-drug delivery²⁶.

In the present paper we will describe the studies on viscosity and stability of nanofluid by UV-absorbance, effects of pH on dispersion properties, TEM analysis and thermal conductivity of different types of nanofluids.

Results and discussion

Viscosity of CuO nanofluid :

Viscosity of nanofluids is an important parameter for practical applications since it directly affects the pressure drop in forced convection. Therefore, for enabling the usage of nanofluids in practical applications, the extent of viscosity increase of nanofluids with respect to base fluids should be thoroughly investigated.

The viscosity of water, ethylene glycol and EG : water (60 : 40) base fluid and their corresponding CuO dispersed nanofluid are given in Fig. 1. The viscosity of ethylene glycol base fluid was greater than that of water base fluid. Similarly, viscosity of ethylene glycol base nanofluid was more than that of water based nanofluid. But in case of ethylene glycol : water (60 : 40) based nanofluid, the viscosity was reduced in comparison to

ethylene glycol based nanofluid due to the mixing of 40% water. Thus it is clear that the viscosity of ethylene glycol based nanofluid is highest in comparison to other nanofluids.

Dispersion studies of CuO nanoparticles :

Dispersion characteristics of copper oxide nanofluids were determined using UV-Visible absorption spectrophotometer.

Effect of surfactant on the absorbances of nanofluids :

Absorbances of nanofluid without surfactant and with surfactant are given in Fig. 2. The nanofluids were prepared by dispersing 0.1% CuO nanoparticles in each of water, ethylene glycol and ethylene glycol/water (60 : 40) base fluids. In case of nanofluids without surfactant, the absorbance values varied from about 0.5 to 0.8. The absorbance value of EG : water (60 : 40) based nanofluid (without surfactant) was maximum as compared to EG and water based nanofluid. Similarly, in the case of nanofluid with surfactant, the absorbance value was 2.5 for EG : water (60 : 40) system which was higher than the EG and water systems having absorbance values of about 1.2 and 0.8 respectively. Thus it can be seen that the absorbance value of EG : water based nanofluid was highest for both with or without surfactant. So dispersion in EG : water based nanofluid was best among the three nanofluids.

Effect of concentration (%) of CuO on the absorbancy of EG : water based nanofluid :

UV spectrophotometer was used to draw the photo-absorbance curve of the CuO nanofluid. The studied range varied from 230–700 nm and the results are given in Table 1. Nine compositions of nanofluids have been pre-

Fig. 1. Viscosities of various base fluids and their corresponding CuO nanofluids.

Fig. 2. Absorbance values of dispersion of 0.1% CuO nanoparticles in different fluids.

Table 1. UV absorbance of nanofluid at varying concentration of CuO nanoparticle in EG : water base fluid

Sr. No.	Concentration of CuO (%)	Absorbance
1.	0.1	0.384
2.	0.2	0.867
3.	0.3	1.337
4.	0.4	1.613
5.	0.5	1.812
6.	0.6	1.912
7.	0.7	2.134
8.	0.8	2.081
9.	0.9	1.982

pared using 0.1–0.9% concentration of CuO nanoparticles (Table 1) in EG : water base fluid. In case of CuO dispersed nanofluid (0.1–0.9%), it was observed that the absorbance increased till CuO concentration 0.7% (2.134) after which it started to decrease (Fig. 3). Thus 0.7% concentration of CuO is optimum for loading of nanoparticles in EG : water base fluid.

Effect of pH on absorbance and dispersion of nanoparticle in 0.1% CuO-EG : water nanofluid :

Lower concentration (0.1%) of copper oxide nanoparticle was selected for the pH dependence study of nanofluid. The nanofluid was prepared by dispersing 0.1% CuO nanoparticles in EG : W system. The pH values of nanofluid were adjusted by using the solutions of NaOH and HCl from 2 to 12. Absorbance of the prepared nanofluid was determined at different pH. Absorbance increased with increase in pH indicating that better dispersion of nanoparticles took place at higher pH (Fig. 4). At pH 10, highest absorbance indicated best dispersion of the nanofluid.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis of CuO nanofluid :

TEM analysis of EG : W (60 : 40) based CuO (0.1%) nanofluid was carried out for determination of agglomeration in the developed nanofluid. The micrographs of 0.1% CuO nanofluids with and without surfactant are given in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. It has been seen that size of CuO nanoparticles varied from 18.2–110.0 nm in case of nanofluid without surfactant whereas size of CuO nanoparticles varied from 15.6–89.3 nm in case of nanofluid with surfactant. This is clearly indicating that addition of surfactant in the nanofluid reduced the agglomeration of nanoparticles.

Thermal conductivity of CuO nanofluid :

The thermal conductivity of water and EG : water (60 : 40) base fluid and its nanofluids with surfactant and without surfactant was determined at 25 °C. For the preparation of nanofluids, 0.1% concentration CuO nanoparticles was used. Thermal conductivity of water and EG : water (60 : 40) base fluid was 0.6090 W/mK and 0.2613 W/mK respectively (Table 2). In case of water based nanofluid, 13.6% enhancement without surfactant, and with surfactant 17.4% enhancement of thermal conductivity were observed over their base fluid. In case of EG : water (60 : 40) based nanofluid, 6.2% and 19.6% enhancement of thermal conductivity were recorded for systems without surfactant and with surfactant respectively. The results show that nearly 10–20% enhancement in thermal conductivity has taken place for dispersion of 0.1% CuO nanoparticles in various nanofluid. Maximum 19.6% thermal conductivity enhancement was observed in case of EG : water with surfactant system.

Polypropylene glycol (PPG) based CNT nanofluid :

Experiments were conducted by dispersing 0.2% of carbon nanotube in PPG with and without surfactant. The selection of 0.2% of carbon nanotube (CNT) in PPG based nanofluids because lower concentration of CNT has less chance of agglomerations. Many researchers also choose lower concentration of CNT in different base fluids (water, ethylene glycol, etc.) but PPG based CNT nanofluid are rare^{27–32}. It was observed that 0.2% concentration of carbon nanotube with and without surfactant gave better dispersion resulting in about 50% enhancement in thermal conductivity.

Fig. 3. Absorbance of various concentrations of CuO in EG : water based nanofluid.

Fig. 4. Absorbance of 0.1% CuO in EG : water based nanofluid at various pH values.

Fig. 5. TEM image of EG : W (60 : 40) based 0.1% CuO nanofluid (without surfactant).

Fig. 6. TEM image of EG : W (60 : 40) based 0.1% CuO nanofluid (with surfactant).

Thermal conductivity of PPG based CNT nanofluid :

The thermal conductivity of PPG base fluid and its

CNT nanofluid without and with surfactant were conducted at 25 °C. The thermal conductivity of PPG base

Table 2. Thermal conductivity of base fluids and their corresponding nanofluids having 0.1% concentration of CuO

Sr. No.	System	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Enhancement of thermal conductivity over base fluid (%)
1A.	Water base fluid	0.6090	-
1B.	CuO Nanofluid in water (without surfactant)	0.6920	13.6
1C.	CuO Nanofluid in water (with surfactant)	0.7147	17.4
2A.	EG : water base fluid	0.2613	-
2B.	CuO Nanofluid in EG : water (60 : 40) (without surfactant)	0.2776	6.2
2C.	CuO Nanofluid in EG : water (60 : 40) (with surfactant)	0.3124	19.6

fluid was 0.0712 W/mK. Thermal conductivity of CNT nanofluid without surfactant was 0.1050 and with surfactant was 0.1120 W/mK (Table 3); these values shows 47.5% and 57.3% thermal conductivity enhancement respectively over their base fluid. Thus it can be noted that there is substantial increase in thermal conductivity value of PPG based CNT nanofluid with surfactant over its base fluid which is to the tune of 57%.

Table 3. Thermal conductivity of polypropylene glycol base fluid and its nanofluid having 0.2% concentration of dispersed carbon nanotube

Sr. No.	Sample	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Enhancement in thermal conductivity over base fluid (%)
1A.	Polypropylene glycol base fluid	0.0712	-
1B.	Polypropylene glycol based CNT nanofluid (without surfactant)	0.1050	47.5
1C.	Polypropylene glycol based CNT nanofluid (with surfactant)	0.1120	57.3

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis :

TEM analysis of PPG based nanofluids having 0.2% carbon nanotube concentration was carried out for assessing agglomeration in the prepared nanofluid. The micrographs of PPG based nanofluids with and without surfactant are given in Figs. 7 and 8 respectively. It has

been seen that size of carbon nanotube particles varied from 13.2–49.9 nm in case of nanofluid without surfactant whereas size of carbon nanotube particles varied from 11.4–39.0 nm in case of nanofluid with surfactant. Thus it can be observed that, when surfactant was added into the nanofluid the agglomerations of nanoparticles were reduced.

Fig. 7. TEM image of carbon nanotube dispersed in polypropylene glycol based nanofluid without surfactant.

Fig. 8. TEM image of carbon nanotube dispersed in polypropylene glycol based nanofluid with surfactant.

Experimental

Four base fluids such as water, ethylene glycol, ethylene glycol : water (60 : 40) and polypropylene glycol (PPG) were used for the preparation of nanofluids. Sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) was used as a surfactant in all the experiments. Ethylene glycol and sodium lauryl sul-

fate were procured from SD-fine chemicals, polypropylene glycol (PPG-2000) was procured from Bayer Material Science LCC, Pittsburgh, USA. Copper oxide nanopowder and carbon nanotube were procured from Intelligent Material Pvt. Ltd., USA. All chemicals were used as such without further purification.

Viscosities of nanofluids were measured by Brookfield viscometer (Model RVDV-II+ Pro, Brook field engineering laboratory USA). UV absorbances of nanofluids were recorded by UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV-1700 Pharmaspec, Shimadzu, Japan). Compact and versatile Thermal constant analyzer (Model TPS-500, Hot disc AB, Sweden) were used for thermal conductivity measurement. TEM analyses were carried out using a Transmission Electron Microscope (Model CM-10, Philips, USA).

Preparation of nanofluids :

Four types of nanofluid have been prepared for carrying out the experiments which are as follows :

(1) Water based nanofluid; (2) Ethylene glycol based nanofluid; (3) Ethylene glycol/water (60 : 40) based nanofluid; (4) Polypropylene (PPG) based nanofluid

Copper oxide nanoparticles and carbon nanotube were dispersed in different base fluids to prepare nanofluids. No. 1 to 3 nanofluids were prepared by dispersing copper oxide nanoparticles in water, ethylene glycol and ethylene glycol/water (60 : 40) separately with and without surfactants. No. 4 type of nanofluid was prepared by dispersing carbon nanotube in polypropylene glycol (PPG) base fluid without surfactant and with SLS surfactant. In all the cases, the mixture of base fluid and nanoparticles were stirred for 3 h at 350 rpm using a magnetic stirrer and subsequently sonicated for 2 h.

Conclusions

On the basis of above studies, it can be concluded that :

- The viscosity of ethylene glycol based nanofluid is highest as compared to other nanofluids.
- The absorbance value of EG : water based nanofluid was highest for systems with or without surfactant indicating that dispersion in EG : water based nanofluid was best among the three nanofluids.
- The 0.7% concentration of CuO is optimum for loading of nanoparticles in EG : water base fluid

because absorbance value was high at this particular concentration.

- At pH 10, highest absorbance of EG : water (60 : 40) based CuO (0.1%) nanofluid indicated best dispersion of the CuO nanofluid.
- TEM analysis indicating that addition of surfactant in the CuO and CNT nanofluid reduced the agglomeration of nanoparticles.
- Maximum 19.6% enhancement in thermal conductivity was observed in case of EG : water based CuO nanofluid system with surfactant while in the case of PPG based CNT nanofluid with surfactant, there was substantial increase in thermal conductivity value over its base fluid which is to the tune of 57%.

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References

1. S. U. S. Choi, in : D. A. Singer and H. P. Wang, "Development and Application of Non Newtonian Flows", ASME, New York, 1995, Vol. FED 231, p. 99.
2. J. A. Eastman, U. S. Choi, L. J. Thompson and S. Lee, *Mater. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 1996, **457**, 3.
3. M.-S. Liu, M.-C. Lin, I.-Te Huang and C.-C. Wang, *Chem. Eng. Technol.*, 2006, **29**, 72.
4. R. Ravisankar, V. S. K. Venktachalapathy, D. N. Alagumurthy and K. Thamizhmaran, *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology (IJEST)*, 2014, **6**, 63.
5. Y. Hwang, H. S. K. Par, J. K. Lee and W. H. Jung, *Curr. Appl. Phys.*, 2006, **6**, e67.
6. W. Yu, H. Xie, L. Chen and Y. Li, *Thermochim. Acta*, 2009, **491**, 92.
7. H. A. Mintsu, G. Roy, C. T. Nguyen and D. Doucet, *Int. J. Therm. Sci.*, 2009, **48**, 363.
8. S. Zeinali Heris, M. Nasr Esfahany and S. G. Etemad, *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, 2007, **28**, 203.
9. D. Kim, Y. Kwon, Y. Cho, C. Li, S. Cheong, Y. Hwang, *et al.*, *Curr. Appl. Phys.*, 2009, **9**, e119.
10. J.-Y. Jung, H.-S. Oh and H.-Y. Kwak, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer*, 2009, **52**, 466.
11. K. V. Sharma, L. S. Sundar and P. K. Sarma, *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transfer*, 2009, **36**, 503.
12. H. Xie, J. Wang, T. Xi, Y. Liu, F. Ai and Q. Wu, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 2002, **91**, 4568.

13. D. Lee, J.-W. Kim and B. G. Kim, *Journal of Physical Chemistry (B)*, 2009, **110**, 4323.
14. A. K. Singh, *Defence Science Journal*, 2008, **58**, 600.
15. V. Trisaksri and S. Wongwises, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2007, **11**, 512.
16. X. Q. Wang and A. S. Mujumdar, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 2007, **46**, 1.
17. S. P. Jang and S. U. S. Choi, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2006, **26**, 2457.
18. H. Xie and L. Chen, *Physics Letters, Section A*, 2009, **373**, 1861.
19. J. Bongiorno, L. W. Hu, S. J. Kim, R. Hannink, B. Truong and E. Forrest, *Nuclear Technology*, 2008, **162**, 80.
20. S. M. H. You, J. Kim and K. H. Kim, *Applied Physics Letters*, 2003, **83**, 3374.
21. J. K. Kim, J. Y. Jung and Y. T. Kang, *International Journal of Refrigeration*, 2006, **29**, 22.
22. M. F. Demirbas, *Energy Sources, Part B*, 2006, **1**, 85.
23. J. Zhou, Z. Wu, Z. Zhang, W. Liu and Q. Xue, *Tribology Letters*, 2000, **8**, 213.
24. L. Vékás, D. Bica and M. V. Avdeev, *China Particuology*, 2007, **5**, 43.
25. L. Zhang, Y. Jiang, Y. Ding, M. Povey and D. York, *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 2007, **9**, 479.
26. A. Vonarbourg, C. Passirani, P. Saulnier and J. P. Benoit, *Biomaterials*, 2006, **27**, 4356.
27. Y. Ding, H. Alias, D. Wen and R. Williams, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer*, 2006, **49**, 240.
28. I. Madni, C.-Y. Hwang, S.-D. Park, Y.-H. Choa and H.-T. Kim, *Colloids Surface*, 2010, **A358**, 101.
29. Maria Alexandra Fonseca, Sylvio Freitas, Bruno Lamas, Bruno Abreu, Hugo Calisto, Nelson Martins and Moinica Oliveira, in "Physical and Chemical Properties of Carbon Nanotubes", eds. Satoru Suzuki, Publish with INTECH, 2013, pp. 4-29.
30. Salma Halefadi, Thierry Maré and Patrice Estellé, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 2014, **53**, 104.
31. Rashmi Walvekar, Ismail Ahmad Faris and Mohammad Khalid, *Heat Transfer-Asian Research*, 2012, **41**, 145.
32. Salma Halefadi, Patrice Estellé, Bahadir Aladag, Nimeti Doner and Thierry Maré, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 2013, **71**, 111.

